

Effects of IATF protocols among housekeeping department's room attendants of selected 4 to 5 star hotels in Manila with safety seal certification

Kyla Nicole T. Pagaduan*, Jade Megumi R. Azor, Derick Lloyd F. Bravo, Charles Randal T. Delacruz, Jerome P. Gagasa, John Andre C. Gomez, Ronald Aron A. Lajera, Andrew Bryle B. Magsino, Cristina D. Sulla

Hospitality Management Department, School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author

Abstract

This paper aimed to analyze and observe the effects of Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) protocols among the Housekeeping Department's room attendants of selected 4-5 star hotels in Manila with safety seal certification. It aimed to identify the challenges that the employees experience in terms of the following indicators: number of employees per day, employees' schedule, employees' requirements before and after their work schedules, and work and activities inside the hotel as they work amidst the pandemic. The researchers conducted an online survey to fifty (50) respondents who work as room attendants in 4- to 5-star hotels in Manila with safety seal certification. The study concluded that the employees experienced an increase in their working hours and days of work, a decrease in their number as workers, changes in the requirements before and after work, and an increase in work and activities. The result suggested that employees must be physically and mentally healthy in order to cope with the effects and changes in work as it could possibly continue to be so due to the unceasing effects of the pandemic.

Keywords: *Inter-Agency Task Force; protocols; housekeeping department; hotels; safety seal certification.*

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Introduction

During crisis, tourism must live up to its responsibility as an integral part of society. People and their well-being must be prioritized in the sector. Even other sectors from across the world have been greatly affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. In Manila, Philippines, many of the hotels have experienced the effect of the pandemic which resulted to some of closing operations temporarily especially during the first months of the pandemic. Other hotels had to reduce the number of their working staff to address the expenses, which is a result of having fewer guests brought about by strict regulations imposed by the government.

In the hotel industry, basic protocols must be followed such as social distancing, use of face masks and/or face shields, and if symptoms of the virus are detected, an immediate medical check-up must be conducted (Christou & Savva, 2022). The room attendants in the hotel industry were among the most affected due to the nature of their work.

The study aims to determine the effects of the mandated Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) protocols among the housekeeping department's room attendants in selected 4-5 star hotels in terms of the number of the following indicators: employees working in a day, employees' schedule, employees' requirements before and after work, as well as works and activities inside the hotel. This study also aims to give recommendations among room attendants to cope with the effects of the IATF protocols.

Hospitality Crisis Management

According to Aliperti et al. (2020), natural disasters and crises pose a particular threat to the hospitality industry; it affects the industries of all sorts in the world, and the impact it has in the hotel industry is devastating as stated by Goodell (2020). Crises such as the pandemic involve a lot of stakeholders, necessitate immediate action, and affect the existing strategy of companies in reaching its goal. The tourism industry suffers a devastating impact. As the pandemic occurs, researches regarding the tourism managements' preparedness have drastically increased. As a result, during a pandemic such as COVID-19, a thorough examination of crisis management procedures is required.

Stecke and Kumar (2009) explained that there is a notable importance in the relationship in trading, especially the supply chains and the small firms for their success in overcoming the challenges brought by the crisis. In times of crisis, improvised marketing practices are very crucial to adapt to its new environment for its success. It was stated by Irvine and Anderson (2004) that reducing the employees working hours is effective in reducing the effects of the natural disasters towards the business. With regards to Hurricane Katrina, a natural disaster, the vulnerability of small businesses was unraveled in terms of the business' unsuccessful communications, tight cash flow, and its inability to manage power outages. However, the owners who somehow thought and acted immediately after experienced less convenience, and eventually were able to have an increase in their sales. There is a lack of contingency plans in the hotel industry in terms of crisis management which eventually results in reactive rather than proactive responses to the crisis.

Most commonly used reactive practices include the utilization of better communication technologies, improvised marketing system, improved training of employees, effective relationship of the stakeholders, and specialist in terms of hygiene protocols; as argued by Garrido-Moreno et al. (2021). A notable example is in Singapore, wherein they utilized adaptable and innovative responses towards the SARS outbreak which eventually allowed them to recover quicker thus opening again. Practices such as those mentioned focus on the domestic market, and the training of employees, and changes in infrastructures with the guidance of the government.

Authorities in Australia imposed a two-week mandatory quarantine and isolation protocols as their strategy in confining and ensuring the safety of its citizens, to the vacationist citizens arriving from other countries. The quarantine facilities during the pandemic, in Western Australia, are the hotels according to the Australian government (Stobart & Duckert, 2022). The work in hospitality management during the pandemic was clearly different from the pre-pandemic. However, the aim to provide quality and excellent service to the guests is still its goal while of course considering their safety. Moreover, due to changes brought about by the pandemic, workers are more expected to have heightened physical and emotional preparedness due to the nature of their work. The satisfaction of the guests is somehow a motivator for the workers to continue their excellent work as stated by Chen et al. (2015).

According to Goh et al. (2021), the number of those who were infected with the Covid-19 in the hotel industry eventually increased from a single case to multiple. As the working environment becomes more and more dangerous, a number of hotel workers being infected were observed by the time that hotels were turned into quarantine facilities.

New Normal Working Conditions

According to Zhang et al., (2020) the hospitality industry is a service industry in which guest satisfaction and experience are critical and cannot be compromised. As a result, maintaining a high level of safety, security, cleanliness, and hygiene is critical for the industry to provide the highest level of customer satisfaction, and given the Covid-19 situation, the hotel housekeeping department bears a lot of responsibility.

As the coronavirus can be controlled by avoiding contact with virus-infected surfaces, the importance of cleanliness and hygiene in hotels has recently increased (WHO, 2020). There will be changes in the hotel and hospitality industry, some of which will be permanent and some of which will be temporary. The primary focus, though, of the industry will be on hygiene, cleanliness, and sanitation. There will be a new ethical hygiene trend. Hotels will place a premium on assuring guests of their safety. Antibacterial door knobs with creative designs, as well as sheaths, will become more popular (covers for high-rise products). There would be a clear concept in place to restore guest trust while maintaining high hygiene standards.

Safety Seal Certificates

Safety seal certificates ensure that hotels follow the safety standards for both the guests and the workers as well as the availability of their contact information, in case a contact tracing is to be conducted (Desiderio, 2021). Safety seal certificates were granted to the following hotels where the respondents are affiliated with the following: Parque España Residence Hotel Alabang, Crimson Hotel Alabang, Marriott Manila Hotel, Okada Manila, Resorts World Manila, Sofitel Philippine Plaza Manila, Solaire Resort & Casino Manila, The Bayleaf Intramuros, and The Heritage Hotel Manila.

IATF Protocols: Health and Safety Guidelines for Accommodation Establishment Operations in the New Normal

In Section 7 of the IATF Protocols (Romulo-Puyat, 2020), the specific guidelines for the housekeeping personnel are as follows:

- Proper usage of sanitizing solutions and proper utilization of disinfectants must be followed.
- Using equipment including face mask, closed shoes, gloves and disposable coveralls must be followed.
- Wearing of personal protective equipment (PPE) in cleaning the rooms of the guests is necessary.
- Department of Health (DOH) disinfection process must be followed.
- Disposal of used equipment and materials must be in compliance with the DOH guidelines.
- Disinfection routine must be practiced including the washing of hands either by alcohol, or soap and water.
- Assigned cleaning staff must be using waterproof aprons aside from facial protection.
- Changing of clothes is necessary for the personnel after their working hours.
- It is encouraged to be sanitized frequently, especially those public areas in the hotel.

Theoretical Framework

Human Relations Theory

In the Human Relations Theory of Elton Mayo, based from his Hawthorne Experiment, he had come up with the conclusion that preferences were distinct among people and their treatment must not be machine-like. The workplace can be considered as a system of social activities wherein there could be different factors that possibly affect the performance of an employee.

In this study, the Human Relations Theory can be utilized to understand the changes in working conditions, break times, and the length of the workday, as well as the new operations and cleaning protocols established to address the occurrence of COVID-19's new normal in the housekeeping department's work environment specifically the room attendants. This theory can help explain why, regardless of the change, worker productivity always increases. This includes proper communication, staff orientation, and consideration of social aspects that occur in the modern world in order to maintain positive workplace performance and prioritization of workers' needs.

Statement of the Problem

The study will attempt to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Gender
 - 1.3. Name of the hotel where they are employed
 - 1.4. Years of service in the Housekeeping Department
2. What are the effects of the mandated IATF protocols among the Housekeeping Departments' room attendants in terms of:
 - 2.1. Number of employees working in a day
 - 2.2. Employee's schedule
 - 2.3. Employee's requirements before and after their work schedule
 - 2.4. Works and activities inside the hotel
3. What can be done to cope with the effects among the Housekeeping Department's room attendants as they follow the IATF protocols?

Significance of the Study

This research benefits the housekeeping departments of hotels because it focuses on how hotels in Metro Manila can regain stability. Hotels also need to figure out how they can help reduce the number of COVID-19 cases so that their housekeeping divisions are not overburdened. A number of the COVID-19 patients at present are accommodated in lodging houses, mostly in Metro Manila. The housekeeping departments' room attendants are considered front liners in the hotel industry, much like medical attendants or specialists in the medical field.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a quantitative study that used the descriptive method. It helped gather the information needed in the housekeeping department that would relate to its experiences brought by the effects of the protocols imposed by the IATF.

Context and Participants

The researchers identified a group of individuals via social media and would provide an online survey questionnaire form to fifty (50) respondents. The researchers used the random sampling technique in this study, in which the sample was chosen at random as a subset of the total population size. This is to ensure that all the room attendants in the chosen hotel have a chance of being selected as respondents of the study. The respondents are only those who worked as room attendants in the housekeeping departments of selected 4 to 5-star hotels in Metro Manila with safety seal certificates.

Instruments

Self-made survey questionnaires were used to gather data that are necessary for the study. The survey questions are designed to identify the effects brought about by the IATF protocols to the hotel attendants' environment of the selected hotels. The questionnaire consist of close-ended questions; Likert scale was utilized so that the respondents can choose only one from the given choices. Surveys are primarily useful for descriptive research because they cover a large population and ask standardized questions of some or all of its members. The goal is to collect data for the questions that were stated in the statement of the problem which can be analyzed statistically.

Said survey questionnaires will be given to fifty (50) respondents online due to the restrictions caused by Covid-19 pandemic that prohibit the researchers from conducting survey through personal contact. The questionnaire was then validated, and the reliability is tested through pilot testing. A pilot study is defined as “a small scale version, or trial run, carried out in preparation for a major study (Polit & Beck, 2021), using similar participants (De Vos et al., 2011)””; wherein it has a value of .84 Cronbach alpha. The collected data from the respondents were given interpretation through statistical analysis. The researchers used frequency and percentage distribution as a statistical technique and method.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1. Demographic profile of the respondents

Table 1. Age of the respondents (n=50)

Age	Frequency	Percentage
25-29 years old	37	74%
30-34 years old	6	12%
35-40 years old	6	12%
41-45 years old	1	2%

According to Table no. 1.1, in terms of age, thirty-seven (37), or 74% of the respondents belong to the age bracket of 25-29 years old, six (6) or 12% from the age bracket of 30-34 years old, six (6) or 12% from the age bracket of 35-40 years old, one (1) or 2% from the age bracket of 41-45 years old. Therefore, the majority of the respondents come from the age bracket of 20-29 years old.

Table 2. Gender of the respondents (n=50)

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	34	68%
Female	16	32%

As can be seen in Table 2, in terms of gender, thirty-four (34) or 68% of the respondents are males while sixteen (16) or 32% are females. Therefore, the majority of the respondents are males.

Table 3. Name of the hotel they are working at (n=50)

Name of Hotel	Frequency	Percentage
Parque España Residence Hotel Alabang	20	40%
Crimson Hotel Alabang	4	8%
Marriott Manila Hotel	6	12%
Okada Manila	4	8%
Resorts World Manila	4	8%
Sofitel Philippine Plaza Manila	3	6%
Solaire Resort & Casino Manila	4	8%
The Bayleaf Intramuros	2	4%
The Heritage Hotel Manila	3	6%

Table 3 presents the names of the hotels where the respondents are presently employed. Twenty (20) or 40% of the respondents work at Parque España Residence Hotel Alabang, four (4) or 8% are connected with Crimson Hotel Alabang, six (6) or 12% work at Marriott Manila Hotel, four (4) or 8% are employed at Okada Manila, four (4) or 8% work at Resorts World Manila, three (3) or 6% are connected with Sofitel Philippine Plaza Manila, two (2) or 4% work at The Bayleaf Intramuros, three (3) or 6% work at The Heritage Hotel Manila. Therefore, the majority of the respondents are employees of Parque España Residence Hotel Alabang.

Table 4. Years of their service in the housekeeping department (n=50)

Years of Service	Frequency	Percentage
1-3 years	35	70%
3-6 years	13	26%
7-9 years	2	4%

As shown in Table 4, in terms of the years of service of the respondents in the housekeeping department, thirty-five (35) or 70% of the respondents have one to three years of service thirteen (13) or 26% have three to six years of service, while two (2) or 4% of the respondents have seven to nine years of service. Therefore, the majority of the respondents have been working as room attendants for one to three years already.

Problem 2. *Effects faced by the housekeeping department's room attendants following the IATF protocols*

The statements are interpreted using the following:

Table 5. Likert scale interpretations

Rating	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
5 – Strongly Agree (SA)	4.50 - 5.00	Strongly agree
4 – Agree (A)	3.50 - 4.49	Agree
3 – Neither Agree nor Disagree (N)	2.50 - 3.49	Neither agree nor disagree
2 – Disagree (D)	1.50 - 2.49	Disagree
1 – Strongly Disagree (SD)	1.00 - 1.49	Strongly disagree

Table 6. Effects faced by the housekeeping department’s room attendants following the IATF protocols in terms of the number of employees working per day

Question	Weighted mean	Verbal Interpretation
Do you think that there is an increase of workers in your work during the pandemic?	3.28	Neither agree nor disagree
Do you think that there is a decrease of workers in your work during the pandemic?	4.14	Agree

Table 6 determines the effects faced by the housekeeping department’s room attendants following the IATF protocols in terms of the number of employees working per day. The table indicates that the respondents do not agree nor disagree on whether there is an increase of the number of workers in their workplace during the pandemic. The respondents though agree that there is a decrease of workers in their workplace during the pandemic. This implies that the respondents differ in their impressions of the effects from the implementation of the IATF protocols in terms of the number of employees in the workplace.

Table 7. Effects faced by the housekeeping department’s room attendants following the IATF protocols in terms of the number of employee’s schedule

Question	Weighted mean	Verbal Interpretation
Do you think that there is an increase in your working hours during the pandemic as it follows the IATF protocols?	3.82	Agree
Do you think that there is an increase in your working days during the pandemic as it follows the IATF protocols?	3.72	Agree
Do you think that there is a decrease in your working hours during the pandemic as it follows the IATF protocols?	3.48	Neither agree nor disagree
Do you think that there is a decrease in your working days during the pandemic as it follows the IATF protocols?	3.58	Agree

Table 7 identifies the effects faced by the housekeeping department’s room attendants following the IATF protocols in terms of the employee’s schedule. The table indicates that the respondents can agree that there is an increase of their working hours during the pandemic. The respondents can agree that there is an increase in their working days during the pandemic. The respondents can neither agree nor disagree whether there is a decrease in their working hours. The respondents can agree that there is a decrease in their working days. The response is that there is an increase while at the same time there is a decrease in their working hours, implies that the employees experienced different effects in terms of their working hours.

Table 8. Effects faced by the housekeeping department’s room attendants following the IATF protocols in terms of the number of employee’s requirements before and after their work schedule

Question	Weighted mean	Verbal Interpretation
Do you have to wear a face mask/face shield?	4.76	Strongly agree
Do you have to report daily health symptoms form?	4.68	Strongly agree
Do you have to undergo a temperature check?	4.72	Strongly agree
Do you have to do the RT-PCR test?	4.64	Strongly agree
Do you have to wear a PPE (Personal protective equipment) suit?	3.60	Agree
Do you have to show a vaccination card?	4.46	Agree
Do you have to sanitize the cleaning materials?	4.76	Strongly agree

Table 8 presents the results on the effects faced by the housekeeping department’s room attendants following the IATF protocols in terms of the employee's requirements before and after their work schedule. The results show that the respondents strongly agree that they need to wear face mask / face shield when at work. The respondents strongly agree that they need to fill-out a daily health symptoms form. The respondents strongly agree that they have to undergo a temperature check when at work. The respondents strongly agree that they need to undergo reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) before reporting to work. The respondents agree that they have to wear personal protective equipment when at work. The respondents agree that they have to present their vaccination card when reporting to work. The respondents strongly agree that they need to sanitize cleaning materials that are used at work.

Table 9. Effects faced by the housekeeping department’s room attendants following the IATF protocols in terms of the number of employee’s work and activities in the hotel

Question	Weighted mean	Verbal Interpretation
Does your work and activities during the pandemic increase as it follows the IATF protocols?	4.30	Agree
Does your work and activities during the pandemic decrease as it follows the IATF protocols?	3.62	Neither agree nor disagree

Table 9 contains the responses of the respondents based on the effects faced by the housekeeping department’s room attendants following the IATF protocols in terms of the employee's work and activities in the hotel. Findings show that the respondents agree that there is an increase in their work and activities during the pandemic when the IATF protocols are implemented. This means that the respondents neither agree nor disagree that there is a decrease in their work and activities during the pandemic when the IATF protocols are implemented.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study sought to identify the effects experienced by the Housekeeping Departments’ room attendants in Manila as they follow the IATF safety protocols. There are more male respondents as evidenced by the demographic profile, which include among others, age and name of the hotel, years of service. Researchers discovered that some hotels opted to reduce the number of workers due to the pandemic. This is because they are affected to any changes that would occur in their respective hotels. Most respondents shared their sentiments as requirements must be complied before and after their work, to ensure their safety as well as the guests. Respondents also have different responses regarding the decrease in their work and activities. This is due to the fact that some hotels might have or not have increased their workers’ work and activities.

Since majority of the respondents agreed that there was a decrease of the number of workers during the pandemic, the researchers suggested that the room attendants must be prepared physically as the decrease of the number of workers in their division could mean more work. Even though the majority agreed that there was an increase in their working hours and days during the pandemic, the researchers suggested that the room attendants must keep both their physical and mental health in a good state, as the effect of those increases in working hours and days could be very exhausting for them.

As for the decrease of the number of workers in the hotel, it is recommended that the management of the hotel ensures equal shifting of their schedule to ascertain that all workers will still have work; as there is a decrease in the number of workers, it is also recommended that current workers are able to do the job, given a possible reduction of the number of workers. Majority of the respondents agreed that they have to wear face mask / face shield; fill-out a daily-health-symptom form; undergo a temperature check; wear Personal Protective Equipment; present their vaccination card; and sanitize their cleaning materials. Therefore, the researchers recommended that room attendants must always be attentive and be wary to ensure that they follow the above-mentioned requirements at work, as failure to do so could potentially put themselves and the people in the hotel in a great risk caused by the virus.

As it follows the IATF protocols, the researchers suggested that room attendants must be more attentive to their work as it requires proper concentration to ensure that they follow protocols. Room attendants must be physically, emotionally, and mentally prepared so that they can carry on their duties properly. For future applicants as room attendants, the researchers suggested that they do brief research about the possible situation of the hotel they intend to be employed, for the challenges that they might possibly encounter such as the ones presented in this study. For future researchers, since the study is surveyed through questionnaires, the researchers recommend continuing this study with an interview in gathering the data. This way, they will have a chance to determine whether there are other underlying factors that occur which affected the variables; as well as they may be able to follow up some questions to the respondents or gather information as to what the interviewee would respond to them. The researchers also suggested that future researchers will identify possible changes that occur in terms of the implementation of the IATF protocols as it could change depending on the severity of COVID-19 cases in some specific areas.

The researchers intend to learn more about the new normal in the hotel industry's work environment in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic. The research will be conducted in selected 4 to 5-star hotels in Metro Manila with safety seal certificates. The respondents are the housekeeping department's room attendants, and the names of the hotels are indicated as part of the requirement to ensure that the hotel they are affiliated with are 4-5 star hotels. Hotels with 4 to 5-star rating bring significance to this study; as four-star hotels, especially in Metro Manila, have been granted approval to accept guests for staycation, as articulated by Department of Tourism Secretary Bernadette Romulo-Puyat. This study is only for the duration of the pandemic and is not concerned with what happens when the COVID-19 pandemic is over.

References

- Aliperti, G., Nagai, H., & Cruz, A. M. (2020). Communicating risk to tourists: A mental models approach to identifying gaps and misperceptions. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 33, 100615. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2019.100615>
- Chen, C. M., Yang, H. W., Li, E. Y., & Liu, C. C. (2015). How does hotel pricing influence guest satisfaction by the moderating influence of room occupancy? *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 49, 136-138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2015.06.006>
- Christou, P., & Savva, R. (2022). Impacts of the pandemic: the role of 'face masks' in hospitality and tourism service provision. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 25(23), 3747-3760. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2021.2014793>
- Desiderio, L. (2021, April 24). *Guidelines out for safety seal in establishments*. Philippine Star. <https://www.philstar.com/business/2021/04/24/2093331/guidelines-out-safety-seal-establishments>
- De Vos, A. S., Strydom, H. Fouché, C. B., & Delpont, C. S. L. (2011). *Research at grass roots: for the social sciences and human service professions* (4th ed.). Van Schaik Publishers.

- Garrido-Moreno, A., Garcia-Morales, V. J., & Martín-Rojas, R. (2021). Going beyond the curve: Strategic measures to recover hotel activity in times of COVID-19. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 96, 102928. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2021.102928>
- Goh, E., & Baum, T. (2021). Job perceptions of Generation Z hotel employees towards working in COVID-19 quarantine hotels: The role of meaningful work. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 33(5), 1688-1710. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-11-2020-1295>
- Goodell, J. W. (2020). COVID-19 and finance: Agendas for future research. *Finance Research Letters*, 35, 101512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2020.101512>
- Irvine, W., & Anderson, A. R. (2004). Small tourist firms in rural areas: agility, vulnerability and survival in the face of crisis. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 10(4), 229-246. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13552550410544204>
- Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. (2021). *Essentials of nursing research: appraising evidence for nursing practice* (10th ed.). Wolters Kluwer.
- Romulo-Puyat, B. (2020, September 24). *Amending further the health and safety guidelines governing the operations of accommodation establishments under the new normal* [Memorandum]. Department of Tourism. <http://www.tourism.gov.ph/files/publications/MC%20No.%202020-002-B.pdf>
- Stecke, K. E., & Kumar, S. (2009). Sources of supply chain disruptions, factors that breed vulnerability, and mitigating strategies. *Journal of Marketing Channels*, 16(3), 193-226. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10466690902932551>
- Stobart, A., & Duckett, S. (2022). Australia's response to COVID-19. *Health Economics, Policy and Law*, 17(1), 95-106. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1744133121000244>
- World Health Organization. (2020, August 25). *COVID-19 management in hotels and other entities of the accommodation sector*. World Health Organization. <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/333992/WHO-2019-nCoV-Hotels-2020.3-eng.pdf?sequence=1>
- Zhang, D., Tu, J., Zhou, L., & Yu, Z. (2020). Higher tourism specialization, better hotel industry efficiency? *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 87, 102509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102509>